

Through collaboration between researchers, Indigenous Peoples and other Arctic residents, services overall improve emergency preparedness, food security, and adaptation to climate change and socio-economic changes.

Investing in climate services and integrating this information into action can have wide-ranging effects on decision-making, society, and the surrounding environment. How can we assess the benefits and costs comprehensively, taking all societal impacts (economic, environmental and social) into account?

By evaluating the wide variety of impacts of climate services, we can determine how to allocate resources most appropriately when considering both the objectives of a decision or a policy and the priorities of a community.

The Arctic service developed by Arctic PASSION support Indigenous Peoples and other Arctic residents by preserving and sharing knowledge, monitoring and informing decisions in communities affected by permafrost degradation, and by strengthening inclusive decision-making. They also provide vital environmental data, wildfire information, air-pollution forecasts, and improve safety and cost-efficiency through lake ice and sea ice monitoring.

Event Database

preserving the Indigenous Knowledge, Traditional Knowledge and Local Knowledge combined with Community-Based Monitoring

Arctic marine climate change and living resources

supporting local and scientific data needs, encompassing inclusive decision-making and enhancing local capacity.

INFRA

better awareness and understanding of wildfires in the Arctic

AURORAE

better awareness and understanding of air pollution migration and deposition in the Arctic

ALEX

monitoring of surface changes and enabling informed decisions related to activities sensitive to permafrost thaw, such as site selection in subsistence, infrastructure and leisure.

State of the Arctic Environment

a way to access comprehensive information on the current state of the environment, supporting a wider understanding of the environmental indicators in the Arctic.

LIS

accurate information about the lake ice results in safety improvements, avoided (in-situ monitoring and recreational) trip costs, optimised production in hydroelectricity and flood risk monitoring.

POLARIS

provides information to ships sailing in ice-covered Arctic seas to make more informed navigation decisions, resulting in avoided social and private costs.

Recommendations

Public investment in large-scale climate and environmental monitoring systems demands accountability and evidence-based decisions. To ensure public funds are used effectively and equitably, these efforts must be guided by inclusive, comprehensive assessments of societal benefits.